

Stiffened web panel in compressed zone of steel connections

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ABSTRACT

Transverse stiffeners in the compressed zone of beam-to-column steel connections are generally welded on the full height of the web panel. In some situations, the stiffeners can be welded only on a part of the web panel. These stiffeners are used to increase the resistance of the panels mainly regarding local buckling. To evaluate the behavior of these stiffened webs, an experimental campaign was carried out on four steel sections of different dimensions fully or partially stiffened. The stiffeners are welded on one or two sides of the web panel. A finite element model using shell elements with non-linear behaviour of steel, geometrical imperfections and large displacements is carried out. The numerical model is validated comparing its results with those of the experimental tests considering the load-displacement curves and the failure modes. Then the model is used to carry out a parametric study by varying the dimensions and geometries of the compressed zones of connections in order to create results that make it possible to discuss the analytical formulas used for engineering practice.

Keywords: transverse stiffeners, beam to column steel connections, experimental tests, numerical model.

1 INTRODUCTION

Reinforcement of web panels under compression is necessary to reduce buckling. In beam-post connections, the compressed zone can be reinforced with transverse stiffeners over the entire depth of the web, or just part of it.

(1–4) have carried out tests on steel column-beam connections and steel sections to model the compression zone of a double-compression section connection. The test results validate that the problem of this zone can be addressed by considering a metal section subjected to patch loading over a width equivalent to that of the force diffusion in the connection. The work also focuses on compressed metal sections. Let's face it, the treatment of stiffeners in compression is a little-discussed subject (5,6). On the contrary, if we're talking about shear stiffeners,(7–9) we've talked about this subject, and every time the transverse stiffener comes in to take up the shear or to help a transverse stiffener distribute the web into sub-webs, which acts on the warping of the block.

EN deals with the subject of stiffeners in compression. This involves determining the cross-section to be considered when assessing linear elastic buckling behavior. (10) has developed the (11) approach for the calculation of transversely stiffened plates. This method concerns a plate with one or more stiffeners and subjected to linear compression on both sides. The subject may seem similar to our case study, but certain differences mean that there is a huge gap between the profile of an assembly and the EN plate. In the case of plates, there are no footings and no patch loading. These are necessary conditions for the representative case of the compression zone of an assembly.

AASHTO (12) proposes the case of compressed stiffeners making up part of the profile height. In fact, if you look inside, you'll find that these are recommendations for construction. Nowhere do we find a procedure for calculating the resistance of this type of stiffened profile, or a study of their behavior.

This document presents all the tests carried out on metal sections, both stiffened and unstiffened. The behavior of this type of stiffener is studied not only through direct observation of experimental test results, but also through the results of the numerical model built on the basis of CASTEM software (13). The parametric study provides a better understanding of the behavior of transverse stiffeners and establishes a basis for defining the strength of this type of profile.

2 EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

The experimental study is a compression study of a set of stiffened or unstiffened metal sections.

2.1 Test sections

The experimental studies are divided into 2 campaigns. The first concerns 12 large PRS sections with symmetrical stiffeners on either side of the web, over the entire height. These stiffeners are arranged in the central zone of the panel or near the edge. In this way, the behavior of walls with these two stiffener positions is compared with that of the same wall without stiffeners.

The second campaign involves the study of PRS and rolled sections on isolated sections with the stiffeners positioned at mid-length. For this second campaign, a set of 12 metal sections were tested in double compression.

The tests carried out enabled us to observe the failure modes of the sections for different transverse stiffening configurations.

2.1.1 Test campaign 1

During the tests, the application of the double symmetrical compression is ensured by the jack through a 100 mm wide wedge on two sides (see Fig. 1). The geometrical and mechanical characteristics are summarizing in tables 1 and 2. Note that all dimensions mentioned in Fig. 1 are in millimeter (mm).

Fig. 1. Test campaign 1 configuration

Table 1. Geometrical characteristics of the campaign 1 specimens [mm]

Panel	h_w	t_w	b_f	t_f	h_s	t_s
B5_RWP 508	488	6	200	10	488	10
B3_RWP 370	349	6	200	10	349	10

Table 2. Mechanical characteristics of the campaign 1 specimens

Coupon	Thickness [mm]	f_y [MPa]	f_u [MPa]
Web	6	360.1	517.7
Flange and Stiffener	10	358.0	521.3

The nomination of each specimen is described in Table.3.

Table 3. Description of the campaign 1 specimens

Name	Description
B3-S0	RWP of 370 mm of height without stiffener
B3-Sp	RWP of 370 mm of height with intermediate stiffener
B3-Se	RWP of 370 mm of height with edge stiffener
B5-S0	RWP of 508 mm of height without stiffener
B5-Sp	RWP of 508 mm of height with intermediate stiffener
B5-Se	RWP of 508 mm of height with edge stiffener

2.1.2 Test campaign 2

Here, six specimens were taken from hot rolled I sections and the other six are welded I sections. In each group of six specimens, one is without stiffener. The five stiffened specimens have different positions or dimensions of stiffeners (see Fig. 2 and Table 4). The web thicknesses are equal to 5.5, 7.1 or 12.3 mm. The stiffeners' thicknesses are equal to 5.5 and 8 mm. The stiffeners depths are chosen with reference to the web panel height leading to:

- ✓ $h_s = h_w$ (for stiffeners welded on the full height of the web panel and the flanges),
- ✓ $h_s = 5/6 h_w$ (for stiffeners welded on a part of the web panel height and/or not on the flanges).

The geometrical and mechanical characteristics are summarized in tables 4 and 5.

Fig. 2. Test campaign 2 configuration

Table 4. Geometrical characteristics of the campaign 2 specimens [mm]

Panel	h_w	t_w	b_f	t_f	t_s
Hot rolled I section	278.6	7.1	150	10.7	8
Welded I section	375.4	12.3/5.5	180	12.3	5.5

Table 5. Mechanical characteristics of the campaign 1 specimens

Coupon	Thickness [mm]	f_y [MPa]	f_u [MPa]
Flange	10.7	269.3	408.4
Web	7.1	304.4	421.7
Stiffener	8	320.0	448.0
Web / Stiffener	5.5	360.0	424.0
Web / Flange	12.3	358.4	504.0

The nomination of each specimen is described in Table.6.

Table 6. Description of the campaign 1 specimens

Name	Description
1.U	Unstiffened panel
2.FD	Double side transverse stiffened panel on the Full web height
3.FS	Single side transverse stiffened panel on the Full web height
4P1E	Partial transverse stiffened panel (stiffener welded to web and one End flange)
5.PC	Partial transverse stiffened panel on the Central part of the web height
6.P2E	Partial transverse stiffened panel (stiffener welded to web and two End flange)

In addition, each specimen is named using H, for hot rolled sections, or W_{λ_1} or W_{λ_2} , for welded sections. λ_1 and λ_2 correspond respectively to the web thickness of 5.5 mm and 12.3 mm, respectively. λ is the slenderness calculated as h_w/t_w .

2.2 Results and processing

The results in load-displacement curves are summarized in the figs. 3. a) and b), 4. a) and b), 5. a) and b), 6. and 7. a) and b).

Fig. 3. Load displacement curves a) B5-S0; b) B3-S0

Fig. 4. Load displacement curves a) B5-Sp; b) B3-Sp

Fig. 5. Load displacement curves a) B5-S0; b) B3-S0

Fig. 6. Hot rolled I-sections load displacement curves

Fig. 7. Welded I-sections load displacement curves a) λ_1 ; b) λ_2

Fig. 3 a) and Fig. 3 b) present the curves of the unstiffened walls. The curves of the slender panels (B5-S0) show a linear behavior up to a loading value of about 280 kN corresponding to a displacement of 0.5 mm, then an elasto-plastic phase before the failure load varies between 357.3 and 400.1 kN with a dispersion around the average value of 376.8 kN which does not exceed 4.5 %. B3-S0 shows a linear behavior up to a loading value of about 320 kN corresponding to a displacement of 0.7 mm followed by a maximum value noted as the failure load which varies between 390.2 and 451.3 kN with a dispersion around the average value of 413.1 kN which does not exceed 7 %. Fig. 4 a) and Fig. 4 b) present the curves for the intermediate stiffeners. These curves show a linear behavior until a displacement of about 1 mm which corresponds to a force equal to about 1100 kN. Then, a non-linear behaviour starts, followed by a lower but quasi-linear slope until the maximum value of the force considered as the failure load is reached. This value, reached for a displacement between 3 and 4 mm, remains lower than a value of 1377.5 kN with an average of 1343.7 kN for the B5-Sp and lower than 1446.4 kN with an average of 1412.5 kN for the B3-Sp. In Fig. 4 b), it can be observed that the beam B3_Sp_P9 has a different linear behavior than other similar beams. This is due to the fact that the beam has an initial imperfection noticed at the level of the flange and later at the level of the loading wedges installation. Fig. 5 a) and Fig. 5 b) present the curves for the edge stiffeners. The curves show a linear behavior up to a load of about 700 kN and a displacement of about 0.5 mm for the B5-Se and 1000 kN for a displacement of about 0.6 mm for the B3-Se. For this configuration, the participating width of the web at the edge is reduced and it is this free part that goes into instability first. Then a second slope appears, followed by a failure load that does not exceed 1368.3 kN for the B5-Se and 1233.9 kN for the B3-Se corresponding to a displacement of about 3 mm. Comparing the two test configurations Sp and Se, it is shown that the participating length of the web affects the stiffener's

behavior with respect to its strength capacity. An edge stiffener resists less than an intermediate stiffener (by 11 % between B5-Sp and B5-Se and by about 14 % between B3-Sp and B3-Se).

Fig. 6 compares the force-displacement curves of different beam configurations derived from hot rolled sections. It can be seen that resistances and stiffnesses increase with the degree of profile stiffening. In addition, there is a significant increase in the plastic bearing compared with the unstiffened section.

A comparison of the curves shows that partial stiffening with a portion of free web at mid-height or at the bottom provides a very similar contribution to strength. On the other hand, it is interesting to note that a stiffener of the same size but arranged in the middle of the web, thus leaving an equal proportion of unstiffened web on either side of the stiffener, provides significantly greater strength.

This observation can be explained by the fact that the free web height on either side of the stiffener is 2 times lower than the free web height in the other 2 stiffener configurations. However, it is interesting to note that connecting the stiffener to the flanges increases the section's strength by more than 23%. Next, Fig.7 a) shows the results of welded sections with a web height-to-thickness ratio λ_1 of 30.52, while the Fig.7 b) corresponds to the welded sections with a web height-to-thickness ratio λ_2 of 68.25. here we note the same remarks for the full-height stiffeners. However, for partial stiffeners, a stiffener welded on both flanges and part of the web is more resistant than a stiffener welded in the middle of the web panel.

3 NUMERICAL STRUDY

3.1 Construction

The finite element model (FEM) has been developed using the Cast3m software. It allows to consider the geometrical and material nonlinearities. The developed model uses triangular shell elements of DKT type (3 nodes). The chosen mesh size is 20×20 mm. This choice of size was based on a convergence study of the mesh. The adopted boundary conditions are calibrated with respect to the experimental test conditions. The translations U_x and U_z are blocked for the loaded surface (surf 2) and all translations and rotations of the surface (surf1) are restricted. Fig. 12 represents the boundary conditions adopted for this model. The loading is applied by imposed displacement in the U_y direction. The yield stresses of the panel elements are those determined by tests (Table 2). A perfectly plastic elastic model characterizes the behavior law of the material used for the model. In fact, the load-deformation curves show a maximum deformation of the compressed panel that occurs in the area of the elastic step of the stress–strain curve associated with a perfectly plastic elastic behavior.

Fig. 8. Finite element model

The Poisson's ratio of the steel is taken equal to 0.3. The shape of the initial geometrical imperfections is in accordance with the first instability mode with a maximum amplitude defined by Eurocode 3 as the minimum between the ratios $h_w/200$ and $a/200$. These imperfections concern the web and the stiffener.

3.2 Validation

3.2.1 Load displacement curves

The comparisons of some load–displacement curves between the finite element model and those of the tests are presented in Fig. 9 a), b), c) and d). It is shown that the finite element model provides

curves globally representative of the beam's real behavior.

Fig. 9. Comparison between FE and experimental load-displacement curves a) B5-S0; b) B3-S0; c) 3.FS-H; d) 4.P1E-H

3.2.2 Modes of ruin

The failure modes are also compared, Fig. 10 a) and b) show some profiles after test compared with the FEM after failure.

Fig. 10. Failure mode a) B5-S0; b) 2FD-H

Here we can say that our finite element model is validated.

4 BEHAVIOR OF TRANSVERSE STIFFENERS

The behavior of the stiffener under compression deserves further development. It is observed the behaviour controlled by the unstiffened part if the web in the case of partial stiffened web panels. For the entire height stiffened panels, the buckling of the intermediate and the edge stiffeners is noted. A controlled behavior of the stiffened panels is provided by the stiffener and an adjacent part of the panel. To more define the behavior of this stiffener, a compression and tension loads are applied on the full height stiffened panel. Based on these results and the results of the deformations, it can be concluded that the ruin is undergone by plasticization of the flanges with an upper part of the web and the stiffener. Afterwards, a buckling occurred as instability which is noted by the reduction of the compressive strength in relation to the tension on the curves. These results have been derived from this experimental and numerical study. However, there is no formula in the standard for the calculation of the failure load in the case of transversally stiffened sections. There is a recommendation of the EN (11) that defines a participating length of the web for studying the behavior of a stiffener in compression. This length is equal to $15 \varepsilon t_w$ ($\varepsilon = \sqrt{235/f_y}$) on both sides of the stiffener. Is it also valid for the case of elastoplastic behaviour? The current standards do not specifically address the subject of transversely stiffened walls loaded in double compression. The only information provided in the Eurocode is the participating width of the web panel that must be considered for the calculation of the failure load. However, the lumped method of the Eurocode seems to be conservative. To support these observations numerically, a comparison is made between the critical load determined for this type of panels using the numerical model with that of a cross-section column calculated using the approach given by the Eurocode (11). The latter represents a simplified model of the section including the stiffener and a participating width of the web equal to $15 \varepsilon t_w$ on either side of the stiffener (ε is taken equal to $\sqrt{235/360} = 0.81$). This width is given for the calculation of critical load of stiffener sections in compression in which this section is considered as a column under compression. Fig.11 a) and b) show the dimensions of the panel and the corresponding cross section. The cross section consists of a stiffener which thickness is $t_s = 10$ mm and width is $b_f = 97$ mm on both sides of the web (cross section) of thickness $t_w = 6$ mm. The model, admitting the same boundary conditions as the panel (an embedding due to the presence of the flanges), is built on the same basis as the panels, see Fig. 11 c). It is a DKT shell element model. The behavior is elastic and perfectly plastic. The boundary conditions respect the presence of the flanges in the case of a stiffened panel. It is a bi-embedded column.

Fig. 11. Tested panel and representative cross section a) stiffened panel; b) representative cross section; c) finite element model of the cross section

Table 7 shows the difference between the critical load of a cross section formed by the stiffener section and $15 \varepsilon t_w$ on both sides of the web section and that of a transversally stiffened panel already tested in the experiment. It is expected that the cross section proposed by the EN (11) represents the behavior of the stiffened panel but only for the calculation of the critical load. Several parameters are

varied to treat different cases of calculation. Firstly, the height of the panel is fixed at $h_w = 369$ mm, the section of the web is varied t_w (4, 6, 10 mm) for a stiffener of t_s of 6 mm. Secondly, the section of the stiffener t_s is varied in the second part (4 and 10 mm) for a thickness of the web t_w of 6 mm. Finally, for a height $h_w = 369$ mm and a web of $t_w = 6$ mm and a stiffener of $t_s = 6$ mm the value of the width of the stiffener b_s equivalent to the width of the flange b_f is taken equal to “a” and then greater than “a”. a, in recall, is the width of the panel.

Table 7. Critical loads of a cross section and transversally stiffened panel

For $h_w = 369$ mm and $t_s = 6$ mm			
t_w (mm)	F_{cr} (cross section) (kN)	F_{cr} (Panel) (kN)	Diff.* (%)
4	1259.4	1362.3	7.5
6	1519.1	1598.5	4.9
10	2125.3	2283.9	6.9
For $h_w = 369$ mm and $t_w = 6$ mm			
t_s (mm)	F_{cr} (cross section) (kN)	F_{cr} (Panel) (kN)	Diff.* (%)
4	735.9	728.5	-1.0
10	5424.3	5498.0	1.3
For $h_w = 369$ mm and $t_s = t_w = 6$ mm			
b_f	F_{cr} (cross section) (kN)	F_{cr} (Panel) (kN)	Diff.* (%)
= a	1426.9	1494.3	4.5
> a	1503.3	1494.3	-0.6

$$*Diff. = \frac{F_{cr,Panel} - F_{cr,cross\ section}}{F_{cr,Panel}} \times 100$$

From Table 7, the maximum difference is 7.5 % between the critical load of a cross-section in buckling and that of the panel determined by varying the different geometric parameters of the sections. Finally, the simplified model of the cross-section perfectly represents a stiffened panel for the determination of its critical load. Thus, a stiffener in compression undergoes buckling and can be assimilated in elastic behavior to a column of cross-section equivalent to that of the stiffener and an adjacent part of the web. However, this is not the case if we want to determine the plastic resistance or the failure load of these two models. For the determination of the plastic resistance, it is necessary to use the FEM model and apply a tension in both cases (panel and cross section).

By comparing between the plastic strengths values of the stiffened panel and the representative cross section we can know if the cross section still represents the stiffened section for the calculation of its plastic strength. Table 8 shows the comparisons of the plastic strengths between the representative column and the stiffened panel. According to the results in Table 8 the cross-section recommended by EN (11) does not represent the behavior of a transversely stiffened panel for the calculation of plastic resistance. It is necessary to search for the model that represents the panel for the plastic strength calculation in order to subsequently find a design expression for the failure load of the stiffened panel.

Table 8. Plastic strengths of cross section and the stiffened panel

F_y (cross section) (kN)	F_y (Panel) (kN)	Diff.* (%)
1021.9	1414.2	-27.7

$$*Diff. = \frac{F_{y,cross\ section} - F_{y,Panel}}{F_{y,Panel}} \times 100$$

5 CONCLUSIONS

The transverse stiffeners under double patch loading are mainly compressed. they used to reinforce the compressed zone in a symmetrical column-to-beam connection. Their behavior depends not only on their geometries but also on their shapes and their mode of connections with the beam they reinforce. An experimental study is carried out to test the behavior of this type of stiffeners. A middle

pan, full or partial and full edge stiffeners are posed under compression. An unstiffened part-controlled behaviour is noted in the case of partial stiffened. A buckling behavior is mentioned in the full height stiffeners. The part web of the panels near to the stiffeners undergo a buckling manipulated by the stiffener deformation. Experimental results must be reinforced by a numerical model to explain some behaviors and to be able to put in place some parametric studies. The finite element model is constructed in the base of the Castem software and validated by being compared to the experimental results in terms of load–displacement curves and failure modes. It's concluded that the imperfection especially in the flanges has affected some results. Generally, the finite element model represents the experimental results. Using the numerical model, it is verified that a transverse stiffener under compression can be analysed as a cross section column to determinate the critical load of the transversally stiffened panel. However, this cross-section can't represent the plastic behavior of the transverse stiffened panel under compression. As a result, engineers can calculate the critical load of a compressed transversely stiffened panel by using one of the formulas given by EN(11) to calculate the critical load of a column in flexion, torsional, or flexion-torsional buckling. This column must have the same geometric characteristics of a cross section representing the stiffener and a part of the web panel. The part of the web panel participating in this formula is given as $15 \epsilon t_w$ on both stiffener sides. The study in this article gives the behavior analysis of a compressed stiffener, the way to calculate its critical load and the limitations of considering the cross-section column as a model to represent the hole behavior of a transverse stiffened panel. This paper is a part of the set-up of an approach to calculate the failure load of a transversely stiffened panel subjected to compression.

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